

Link-State-Aware and Topology-Aware Dynamic Resource Allocation in Spatially Multiplexed EONs

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Abstract—Space Division Multiplexed-Elastic Optical Networks (SDM-EONs) are anticipated to emerge as the predominant technology for future optical networks that offer high capacity and flexibility. Under dynamic traffic conditions, some network links become highly congested and tend to block more requests compared to other links. As a result, it becomes challenging to fully utilize the networks' capacity. The most commonly used routing algorithm in optical networks does not consider the distribution of traffic among network links. In this work, we demonstrate a dynamic route-finding approach for resource allocation in SDM-EONs, leveraging network links' spectrum occupancy status and the network's topological characteristics to find alternative paths. The present study involves the development and evaluation of the link-state aware and topology-aware routing, modulation, core and spectrum assignment (RMCSA) algorithm for SDM-EONs, which considers congestion avoidance policy to compute alternative candidate paths and also ensures the availability of at least two link-disjoint candidate routes between each source-destination pair. The performance of the proposed algorithm is evaluated using an event-driven simulator on two realistic network topologies. The simulation findings provide empirical evidence that our suggested method effectively reduces connection blocking and optimizes the utilization of available spectrum resources compared to benchmark K-shortest paths-based RMCSA, congestion-aware RMCSA, and K-Disjoint paths-based RMCSA algorithms.

Index Terms—elastic-optical networks; link-state-aware; multi-core fiber; optical networks; routing, modulation, core and spectrum assignment; space division multiplexing

I. INTRODUCTION

In the past decade, there has been an exponential rise in global Internet traffic owing to the proliferation of data-hungry applications like cloud computing, video conferencing, online gaming and 5G mobile communications [1]. This exponential rise in IP traffic is fueled by the two-fold increase in active Internet users and the average daily data usage by individual users. Since optical transport networks carry most of the aggregated traffic, they are the backbone of global Internet services. Therefore, to cope with these ever-increasing demands, there is a need to push the capacity of the optical transport networks.

Elastic Optical Networks (EONs) are one of the solutions to increase the spectral efficiency of existing single-mode fiber-based optical networks. EONs can increase the capacity of existing optical networks by exploiting flexible bandwidth allocation techniques and utilizing spectrum-efficient modulation formats [2]. So far, EON's application with single-mode fibre has been studied and explored. However, the capacity of

a single-mode optical fibre-based network has almost reached its nonlinear limit [3]. Therefore, there is a need for more scalable, cost and energy-efficient Internet and networking solutions [4].

Nowadays, researchers are exploiting spatial domains for high-speed data transmission. SDM-EONs are emerging as a viable option to scale the capacity of long-haul and data-centre-based networks [5]. Multi-core Fibers (MCF), few-mode fibers, and multiple fiber bundles are a few SDM-enabling approaches. Among these SDM techniques, MCF-based SDM-EONs can scale the capacity significantly with reduced cost per bit [6]. However, MCF-based SDM-EONs face degradation in service due to inter-core crosstalk. Based on the severity of inter-core crosstalk present among the cores, the MCFs are broadly categorized as strongly-coupled, weakly-coupled and uncoupled. Uncoupled MCF-based SDM-EONs possess several advantages over other MCF types, like negligible inter-core crosstalk, high core density per unit area, standard 125 μm cladding diameter and break resistance [7].

One of the major concerns with such networks is the designing of Routing, Modulation, Core and Spectrum Assignment (RMCSA) algorithm [8]. The RMCSA problem is MCF-based SDM-EONs becomes very complex due to the addition of spectrum contiguity and core continuity constraints [9]. To simplify, the RMCSA problem is solved by dividing it into sub-problems, viz. routing and modulation selection problem, core selection problem, and spectrum assignment problem. Conventionally, the routing sub-problem is solved using Dijkstra's shortest path, Yen's K-shortest paths and K-Disjoint paths algorithm. In a simple implementation, Core selection follows first fit, and Spectrum assignment follows first fit or last fit spectrum selection policy. K-Disjoint paths-based route selection diversifies the opportunity to find resources but at the cost of longer hop/path lengths and utilization of more resources. The mentioned algorithms and techniques offer a trade-off between performance and complexity. None of these algorithms considers the variable traffic distribution among the network links.

Recent developments in Software-Defined Networking (SDN) facilitate the central controller to access real-time traffic status [10]. This includes the ability to monitor and analyze network traffic on each link in the network. Authors in [11] have proposed a dynamic routing algorithm based congestion-aware CA-RMCSA algorithm where the alternative path is

found using link spectrum occupancy status to minimize the blocking due to congestion-hotspots. Their proposed CA-RMCSA algorithm performs significantly better than the K-shortest paths-based K-SP-RMCSA algorithm in reducing connection blocking. While computing the alternative paths, the CA-RMCSA algorithm bypasses the links carrying high traffic. However, their proposed algorithm computes only two candidate paths.

In this work, we propose a link-state aware and topology-aware routing, modulation, core and spectrum assignment (RMCSA) algorithm for SDM-EONs, which considers congestion avoidance policy to compute alternative candidate paths. The proposed algorithm also ensures the availability of at least two link-disjoint candidate routes between each source-destination pair.

II. SDM-EON NETWORK MODEL

An SDM-EON is modelled using a graph $G(N, L, C, S)$. Here, N is the set of nodes, and L represents the set of network links. Each link $l \in L$ consists of a pair of bidirectional MCF. C is the total number of cores available in each MCF, and S denotes the number of wavelength slots available in each fiber core. An arrived connection request (CR) is denoted as $r(s, d, b)$ where s and d represent the source and destination nodes, while b denotes the required bandwidth in bits/sec. The number of spectrum slots required (SS_r) for a connection request is computed by using,

$$SS_r = \left\lceil \frac{b}{BW_S \times M} \right\rceil. \quad (1)$$

BW_s is the bandwidth of a single-spectrum slot (sub-channel) in GHz, and M denotes the spectrum efficiency of the modulation format in bits/symbol. When a new CR arrives at the network, the resource allocation algorithm attempts to identify a path between the source (s) and destination (d) nodes where there are unoccupied slots SS_r . This path must adhere to constraints, including spectrum continuity, spectrum contiguity, and core continuity [11]. If the resources are found, a lightpath is established between the s - d pair; otherwise, the CR is blocked.

III. PROBLEM STATEMENT AND RELEVANT WORKS

There are various routing algorithms available in the literature which are used to find a route between a pair of nodes in optical networks. The most prevalent ones are *Dijkstra's shortest path* (SP) [12], *Yen's K-Shortest paths* (K-SP) [13] and *K-Disjoint paths* (K-DP) [14] algorithm. These algorithms have been used invariably for routing sub-problems in optical networks [8], [15], [16]. These algorithms offer a trade-off between blocking performance and computational complexity. The SP routing-based RMCSA algorithm computes only the shortest path between s - d pair. If the resources are not available on the SP, the CR is blocked. On the other hand, the K-SP algorithm computes the first K shortest paths between s - d pair and hence possesses higher computation complexity than the SP algorithm. If the K-SP-RMCSA algorithm cannot find the

resources on the first shortest path, it checks the availability of resources on all K-candidate paths, hence lowering the chances of blocking. However, the K-candidate paths found by the K-SP algorithm may have some links in common. If the blocking happens on the common link, the CR will get blocked on all the candidate paths having that same link in common.

In realistic network topologies, under dynamic traffic scenarios, it is common that some central links get congested earlier than non-central links. As a result, the CRs may get blocked even if the resources are available in networks, thus resulting in under-utilization of available resources. To address this problem, the K-DP algorithm was put forward, which computes K link disjoint paths. The alternative paths found by the K-SP algorithm do not have any links in common. The K-DP performs well for the networks with high average nodal degree (D_{avg}). The K-DP-RMCSA algorithm's performance is limited by the network's availability of K disjoint paths. Further, the K-DP algorithm gives alternative paths whose link lengths are relatively larger as compared to the alternative paths found by the K-SP algorithm. Longer link lengths limit the utilization of higher-order modulation formats, thus forcing the request to require a comparatively higher number of SS_r (Eqn. 1). As a result, the overall spectral efficiency tends to get compromised in SDM-EONs.

To address the above-mentioned trade-offs, we proposed a new method of computing alternative paths in our previous work [11]. The paper proposes a congestion-aware CA-RMCSA algorithm which computes the alternative paths by ignoring the most congested link in the shortest path, as shown in 1. The proposed algorithm with only two candidate paths performs better than the K-SP-based K-SP-RMCSA algorithm with $K = 4$. However, the proposed algorithm could only find two alternative paths. If the path is blocked on the second alternative path, the CR will get blocked. The alternative path given by algorithm [11] may also have some common links with the shortest path since it ignores only the single highest congested path while computing the alternative path. But, the resources may also be available on the third path, which is link-disjoint from the shortest path. The authors found that in almost all real network topologies, namely Europe Network (Fig. 2 (a)), German Network (Fig. 2 (b)), USNET [11], NSF-14 [15], Indian-RailTel [15], JPN-12 [8], every node possesses nodal degree $D \geq 2$. Consequently, two link-disjoint alternate paths can certainly be found in real network topologies.

TABLE I: List of Notations and Symbols

Notation	Description
SOR_{l_n}	Spectrum Occupancy Ratio of n^{th} link
S_o	Total slots occupied on a link
S	Total slots available on a link
R_b	Total number of blocked CRs
R_a	Total number of accepted CRs
TH_r	Holding time of a connection request
H_p	Links in a working path P
τ	Total observation time

Fig. 1: Flowchart of the proposed CA-DP-RMCSA algorithm.

IV. PROPOSED ALGORITHM

This section describes the proposed congestion-aware and disjoint path-based CA-DP-RMCSA algorithm. Taking the facts mentioned in section III into account, we design the proposed CA-DP-RMCSA algorithm, which computes the alternative paths by utilizing the spectrum-occupancy-state of the networks' links as well as the topology of the network to ensure at least two candidate paths are link-disjoint. The flowchart of the CA-DP-RMCSA algorithm is given in Fig. 1. When a CR $r(s, d, b)$ arrives in the network, the algorithm finds the first shortest path between s - d pair by using Dijkstra's SP algorithm. It chooses the highest possible modulation format (M) using Table III and then using Eqn. 1 the algorithm computes the required spectrum slots (SS_r). The algorithm then finds if the resources (SS_r) are available in the first

core in the shortest path, satisfying all constraints. If the resources are unavailable, it searches for the same in the next cores until all the cores get exhausted. If the resources are not available in any of the cores in the shortest paths, the algorithm calls Algorithm 1 to compute the congestion-aware alternative candidate path and checks all cores one by one for the availability of required resources. If the resources are available, the algorithm returns the path P_k , SS_r , core index c and starting slots index SSI . Otherwise, the algorithm calls Algorithm 2 and computes the alternative path, which must be link-disjoint to the shortest path. If the algorithm ceases to find the required slots even in the disjoint path, the CR is blocked, and the algorithm proceeds to process the next requests. As described, the K-CA-DP-RMCSA algorithm computes the alternative paths using different strategies. The first path is computed using Dijkstra's shortest path algorithm. The second path is computed after checking the link-occupancy status of each link in the shortest path, and the third path chosen is the link disjoint from the first-shortest path.

Algorithm 1 CONG-AWARE PATH

- 1: **function** CONG-AWARE PATH($G(N, L, C, S)$, CR(s, d, SS_r), $P_{1s}\{l_1, l_2, \dots, l_n\}$)
 - 2: Fetch the links of the shortest path P_{1s} .
 - 3: For every link, compute $SOR_{l_n} = \frac{S_o}{S}$.
 - 4: Find link with $\max l_{max} = \max(SOR_{l_n})$
 - 5: Set the weight of l_{max} equal to infinity
 - 6: Find the shortest path (P_{2-CA}) between s - d pair.
 - 7: Revert to weight of l_{max} to original weight
 - 8: **Return:** P_{2-CA} .
 - 9: **end function**
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Algorithm 2 K^{th} DISJOINT PATH

- 1: **function** DISJOINT PATH($G(N, L, C, S)$, CR(s, d, SS_r), $P_{1s}\{l_1, l_2, \dots, l_n\}$)
 - 2: Fetch the links of the shortest path P_{1s} .
 - 3: Fetch l_{max} of all ($K-1$) paths
 - 4: Set the weight of each link in the P_{1s} and $l_{max} = \text{inf}$
 - 5: Find the shortest path (P_{3-D}) between s - d pair.
 - 6: Revert the weight of links in the P_{1s} , l_{max} to original
 - 7: **Return:** P_{3-D} .
 - 8: **end function**
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V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To test the performance of the aforementioned RMCSA algorithms, we use two realistic network topologies, EuroNet and German Network, shown in Fig. 2. The physical attributes of both networks are shown in Table II.

A. Simulation Setup

We use an event-driven Python-based simulator to test the performance of the aforementioned algorithm. Each link consists of a pair of MCFs having four uncoupled cores/fibres.

TABLE II: Physical Attributes of Network Topologies

	$ N $	$ L $	D_{avg}	Avg. link length (L_{avg})
EuroNet	28	41	2.93	625.7
German	17	26	3.06	170.3

(a)

(b)

Fig. 2: Network topologies with link length in km: (a) EuroNet, (b) German Network

Core switching is not allowed. So, the core continuity constraint exists in each RMCSA algorithm. Each core has 320 spectrum slots, each of 12.5 GHz. We employ a guard-band policy; hence, we use an extra band of 12.5 GHz (one slot) for each request. The first-fit policy is implemented for core selection sub-problem as well as for spectrum assignment sub-problem. Connection requests on each network node follow the Poisson arrival rate, whereas the holding time of each request is generated using an exponential distribution. When a new CR arrives at a node, the destination node is chosen randomly from $|N|$ with uniform distribution. Similarly, the bandwidth requirement of a CR is chosen randomly from the set δ , $\delta = \{25, 50, 75, 100, 125, 150, 175, 200\}$ in Gbps. The distance

adaptive modulation formats are chosen using Table III.

TABLE III: Modulation formats against path length

Modulation Format	M	Transmission Capacity (Gbps)	Path Length (Km)
DP-BPSK	1	25	8000
DP-QPSK	2	50	4000
DP-8QAM	3	75	2000
DP-16QAM	4	100	1000
DP-32QAM	5	125	500
DP-64QAM	6	150	250

We use $K=3$ for K-SP-RMCSA and K-DP-RMCSA algorithms. Each simulation runs till 10^5 connection requests are served. To record the results in a steady-state scenario, the first 10^3 CRs are not counted. Each simulation is repeated ten times, and results are plotted with 99% confidence interval.

B. Performance Metrics

The primary objective of developing improved RMCSA algorithms is to achieve reduced connection blockage across different levels of traffic load intensity. Secondly, the algorithm should also optimally utilize the available capacity. To evaluate the aforementioned capabilities of an algorithm, we use three performance metrics: Request Blocking Probability (RBP), Network Resource Utilization (NRU) [11] and Average Hop Count (AHC).

$$RBP = \frac{R_b}{R_b + R_a} \quad (2)$$

$$NRU = \frac{\sum_{r \in R_a} SS_r \times H_p \times TH_r}{|S| \times |L| \times |C| \times \tau} \quad (3)$$

$$AHC = \frac{\sum_{r \in R_a} H_p}{R_a} \quad (4)$$

The algorithm with better constraint handling capabilities under dynamic traffic scenarios can improve NRU by potentially leveraging additional resources, reducing the RBP by accommodating higher traffic volumes.

C. Simulation Results

The RBP performance for EuroNet and German Network is shown in Fig. 3. The K-SP-RMCSA method exhibits the highest overall blocking compared to other algorithms. The CA-RMCSA algorithm, as proposed in [11], demonstrate superior performance compared to the K-SP-RMCSA algorithm. The CA-RMCSA technique effectively mitigates blocking by dynamically identifying and utilizing alternative paths to circumvent congested networks during computation. Moreover, in the case of EuroNet topology with an average degree (D_{avg}) less than 3, the K-DP-RMCSA method exhibits reduced blocking at lower load levels. However, at higher load levels, it demonstrates the highest blocking compared to all other algorithms mentioned. In contrast, it can be observed that the K-DP-RMCSA algorithm has comparatively superior performance in the German network ($D_{avg} > 3$) when compared to its performance in the EuroNet topology. The findings suggest a direct relationship between the performance

(a)

(b)

Fig. 3: Request Blocking Probability of (a) EuroNet and (b) German Network

of the K-DP-RMCSA algorithm and the average nodal degree of a network. The proposed K-CA-DP-RMCSA algorithm incorporates the most advantageous aspects of the above-mentioned three algorithms. The first path is selected based on its minimal length, the second path considers congestion, and the third path deliberately chooses to be link-disjoint from the shortest paths. In real optical networks, the presence of two readily available link-disjoint paths is sufficient to meet the requirement. Consequently, the algorithm under consideration exhibits the lowest RBP compared to all the aforementioned algorithms. When compared to the K-SP-RMCSA, CA-RMCSA, and K-DP-RMCSA algorithms, the proposed K-CA-DP-RMCSA algorithm shows a reduction in blocking probability of 14.8%, 10%, and 16.7%, respectively in EuroNet topology. In the German network, the proposed algorithm shows a reduction in blocking probability of 45.6%, 31%, and 17%, respectively, when compared to the K-SP-RMCSA, CA-RMCSA, and K-DP-RMCSA algorithms.

The figure provided in Figure 4 demonstrates the total utilization of resources for the algorithms outlined before. The CA-RMCSA algorithm [11] exhibits a higher NRU than the benchmark K-SP-RMCSA method. The second alternative

(a)

(b)

Fig. 4: Network Resource Utilization of (a) EuroNet and (b) German Network

path of the CA-RMCSA algorithm is designed to check the link's spectrum occupancy ratio, hence reducing the occurrence of blocking caused by continuity and contiguity constraints.

The K-CA-DP-RMCSA technique, as suggested, calculates the third path that is disjoint from the shortest paths. Therefore, it can be inferred that the K-CA-DP-RMCSA algorithm not only enhances the utilization of resources but also mitigates the occurrence of blockage, as explained in the preceding paragraph. However, it should be noted that the K-DP-RMCSA method exhibits the highest level of spectrum utilization. It is important to emphasize that although this algorithm achieves the maximum utilization, it does not necessarily result in the lowest blocking rate. The K-DP-RMCSA algorithm demonstrates a higher level of blocking compared to the suggested CA-DP-RMCSA approach while also exhibiting a greater degree of spectrum utilization. Several factors contribute to this increased utilization of the spectrum. As seen by Equation (3), the NRU is directly proportional to two factors: (i) the total path length of a route, denoted as L_p , and the number of required spectrum slots, denoted as SS_r exhibits a proportional relationship, where L_p represents the path length.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 5: Average Hop Count of (a) EuroNet and (b) German Network

The K-DP-RMCSA, a routing algorithm that prefers longer alternative paths, will likely span more links (H_p); see Fig. 5. Consequently, the demands will necessitate an increase in the value of SS_r and an associated rise of H_p . (ii) The elevated occurrence of blocking can also be attributed to the absence of three link-disjoint routes connecting every s - d pair. In the case of a request $r(s, d, b)$, if either s or d satisfies the condition $D_{avg} < 3$, and the resources are not available on the first two link-disjoint paths, it will be blocked due to the inability of the K-DP-RMCSA algorithm to provide a third link-disjoint path. In contrast, the K-CA-DP-RMCSA algorithm, as presented, necessitates just two link-disjoint pathways, which are widely accessible inside practical network topologies.

VI. CONCLUSION

The present study introduces a novel algorithm, namely the link-congestion-aware and topology-aware RMCSA algorithm, which aims to address the issue of resource allocation in spatially multiplexed elastic optical networks. The technique under consideration utilizes real-time traffic distribution across network links to identify alternative paths that exhibit a reduced likelihood of congestion compared to the alternative shortest paths determined by the benchmark K-shortest paths

algorithm. In order to increase the likelihood of a connection request being accepted, the algorithm seeks out a third alternative path that is disjoint from the first shortest path in terms of links. The simulation findings provide evidence for the better performance of the proposed K-CA-DP-RMCSA algorithm compared to the benchmark algorithms K-SP-RMCSA, CA-RMCSA, and K-DP-RMCSA. For EuroNet topology, the suggested K-CA-DP-RMCSA method demonstrates a reduction in blocking probability of 14.8%, 10%, and 16.7% when compared to the K-SP-RMCSA, CA-RMCSA, and K-DP-RMCSA algorithms, respectively. The proposed algorithm demonstrates a reduction in blocking probability of 45.6%, 31%, and 17% when compared to the K-SP-RMCSA, CA-RMCSA, and K-DP-RMCSA algorithms, respectively, for the German network. Furthermore, the K-CA-DP-RMCSA method exhibits superior efficiency in terms of resource utilization compared to the considered benchmark algorithms.

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